

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

PROMISING RETURN PRACTICES

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KEY FINDINGS

This report systematically presents an inventory of good and promising practices related to return governance from 12 countries, using a common analytical framework. We define these practices as those that actively promote the rights, dignity, and agency of migrants while also contributing to effective and sustainable return governance. In this inventory, each practice is analysed based on its context (geography, duration, target group, return stage), concise description, the return governance implementation challenges it addresses, the principles referenced, concrete benefits, impacts, key lessons learned, and relevant recommendations.

Recurring themes that characterize these practices are summarized below.

1. Creating pathways out of precarious status

Promising practices establish clear, time-bound pathways out of prolonged precarity by linking temporary statuses to realistic prospects for regularisation, onward mobility, or return. Measures such as Germany's *Chancenaufenthaltsrecht* illustrate how legal clarity and predictability can reduce long-term "limbo" situations, while supporting both return planning and integration.

2. Accurate information and counselling in a timely manner

Promising practices prioritise the early provision of clear, accessible and accurate information on legal status, rights, options and remedies throughout the return process. Counselling is most effective when delivered through trusted intermediaries—such as NGOs and independent actors—who help bridge information gaps, support informed decision-making, and strengthen migrants' agency, as illustrated by practices such as Nigeria's Patriotic Citizen Initiative.

3. Prioritising alternatives to detention and individualised case management

Effective practices place non-custodial measures at the centre of return systems, favouring supervision, reporting obligations and community-based arrangements over detention. Examples from Sweden, Greece and Canada demonstrate the value of proportionality assessments, individualised case management, the use of dignified temporary accommodation for migrants, and oversight of detention conditions where deprivation of liberty is used.

4. Embedding multi-actor coordination and local partnerships

More robust approaches rely on structured cooperation between migration authorities, municipalities, civil society organisations and international actors across different stages of return. Practices in Nigeria and Georgia show how coordinated pre-return preparation and post-return reintegration benefit from clearly defined roles, information-sharing mechanisms and locally embedded partnerships.

5. Embedding rights and vulnerability sensitivity in decision-making

Practices that are considered more effective incorporate human rights obligations into return procedures, such as non-refoulement safeguards and assessments that are sensitive to gender and children. Sweden's approach demonstrates how systematically considering vulnerability can influence return decisions and help prevent individuals from facing serious harm. In contrast, Jordan's funding mechanisms aimed at protecting refugees highlight how implementing certain measures can enhance access to education, employment, and healthcare for vulnerable groups.

6. Documenting, monitoring and independent oversight

Practices that are formally documented, monitored and reviewed are more robust and transferable. Digital case systems (Netherlands) and independent monitoring mechanisms involving NGOs (e.g. Greece's Recording Mechanism on informal forced returns) function as accountability tools, mitigating risks of abuse and enabling evaluative learning.

7. Recognising migrant agency within return governance

Stronger practices acknowledge migrants as active participants in return processes by creating space for informed decision-making and dialogue. Initiatives such as go-and-see visits in Türkiye and migrant involvement in reintegration planning in Georgia illustrate how recognising agency can improve both legitimacy and outcomes.

8. Delivering holistic and sustained reintegration support

Promising reintegration practices combine economic assistance, psychosocial support, documentation assistance and community-level interventions, often delivered by local actors. Examples from Georgia, Iraq and Nigeria highlight the importance of engagement both before return and beyond the immediate post-return phase, supported by vocational training, counselling and outcome monitoring. Morocco illustrates how access to healthcare, basic education and social services for regularised returnees can facilitate reintegration, while Afghanistan shows the role of structured assistance packages that extend beyond immediate relief to support longer-term settlement.

Taken together, these dimensions suggest that promising practices in return governance are those that combine legal clarity, proportionality, coordination, monitoring and rights-based safeguards with sustained support and meaningful engagement of migrants and local actors. While context-specific, these features offer transferable lessons for improving return governance across diverse institutional and political settings.

INTRODUCTION

This concept note, prepared as part of WP9 of the GAPs project, aims to identify and categorise “good” and “promising” practices regarding coerced returns. Synthesising findings from GAPs Work Packages 2-9, it proposes both an analytical framework and a standardised structure to support a comparative and multi-dimensional mapping of return-related practices across selected countries.

Return migration is a complex, multi-stage process that includes preparation before returning, the act of leaving, and reintegration after returning. Within this process, “good” or “promising” practices are those that actively promote migrants’ rights, dignity, and agency, while also contributing to effective and sustainable return governance. These practices may be implemented by a range of actors, including state authorities, civil society organisations, international organisations, local authorities and migrant-led initiatives.

Drawing on scholarship on policy transfer and upscaling (Wolman, 2009), as well as debates on “well-governed migration” or “good governance” discussions (Betts 2011; Karabacak et al. 2024; Robinson 2018, 2020; Truong 2006), good practices are understood here not as universally replicable models, but as context-specific approaches that: (1) explicitly or implicitly advance foundational principles such as human rights protection, non-refoulement, accountability, and recognition of migrant agency; (2) address structural and operational challenges identified within return systems; and (3) generate tangible benefits and learning opportunities for other contexts, even if they cannot be directly copied.

In adopting this approach, the framework deliberately distances itself from narrow, state-centric or technocratic understandings of “good governance” that prioritise efficiency or enforcement over rights. Instead, it aligns with critical scholarship that foregrounds protection and decentres return governance by recognising the plurality of actors involved—including civil society organisations, destination and origin country stakeholders—and by taking migrant subjectivities seriously within migration governance processes.

A useful reference point is the AdMiGov project’s definition of “good migration governance” (Garces-Mascareñas et. al., 2023) which links “goodness” to both an instrumental component (effectiveness and efficiency) and a normative component (compliance with key UN agreements such as the New York Declaration, the Global Compacts on Migration and Refugees, and the Sustainable Development Goals). This concept note builds on this definition but reorders its priorities: while effectiveness and efficiency are considered, they are systematically subordinated to compliance with human rights, non-refoulement, do no harm, and migrant agency. In other words, a practice should not be considered “good” solely because it is efficient or yields higher returns; it must also clearly align with international protection standards and respect migrants’ rights and dignity.

On this basis, the concept note adopts a “promising practices” lens, recognising that practices need not be perfect or fully effective to offer valuable insights. The focus is on identifying what works, for whom, under what conditions, and where gaps, risks or unintended effects remain. This approach avoids a simplistic ranking or best-practices labelling and instead centres documented efforts by states, organisations and communities to improve return governance while strengthening protection for migrants. Accordingly, a promising practice does not presume that any single policy is universally optimal but rather draws on evidence to explain its demonstrated effectiveness and its potential (or the promise) relevance in other contexts (see Fazal et.al. 2017 and Kuschminder, 2019).

Good or promising practices in return governance are thus defined here as context-specific policies, programmes, interventions, or projects that have demonstrably improved outcomes for migrants and stakeholders—such as better rights protection, procedural fairness, reintegration prospects or access to legal pathways—while aligning with agreed normative standards. These practices may be temporary or permanent in nature, but must be sufficiently documented to allow learning, adaptation and potential upscaling in other settings. Policy transfer and upscaling are therefore treated as key analytical dimensions in assessing the promise of identified practices.

METHOD

In this report, policies and practices are classified as “good” or “promising” on the basis of a multistep assessment. First, core evaluation dimensions were derived from existing frameworks on identifying and transferring good practices in migration and return policy. These dimensions include:

- (i) normative alignment with international human rights and refugee law;
- (ii) demonstrated effectiveness (for example, improved access to safeguards, reduced rights violations, more sustainable reintegration);
- (iii) relevance and coherence within the national context;
- (iv) the presence of monitoring, evaluation and learning mechanisms.

Second, country experts within the GAPs consortium used these criteria to identify potential practices in the country cases, drawing on comprehensive country reports from WP2–WP9 and discussing options within their national teams. Draft selections were then reviewed and refined by the WP9 coordination team; only practices that met the core criteria of rights compliance and observable positive outcomes for migrants and other stakeholders—and that showed some potential for adaptation under similar conditions—were retained as “promising practices” in this compilation. This step also involved fine-tuning, standardisation, and consistency checks.

Framework Structure

To map and compare these practices systematically, this concept note uses a refined framework organised around four core dimensions:

- i) Guiding principles
- ii) Challenges addressed
- iii) Return stage

Each category is described in detail in the next pages, outlining its purpose and how it can help systematically assess, compare, and map the practices included in the report.

1. PRINCIPLES

Principles refer to the guiding values, often described as the normative and ethical foundations of return policies, that determine whether a practice is legitimate and compliant with international rights standards. The selection of principles draws on the frameworks established by the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration (2018), IOM's policy on the full spectrum of return, readmission and reintegration (2022), and the United Nations Network on Migration (2021).[1] Return policies must be designed and implemented in line with international law and, where applicable, EU legal standards [2], including the principle of non-refoulement, the best interests of the child, and the right to family life

To keep the analysis coherent, we focus on principles that show minimal overlap with the challenges identified in the framework.

a) Non-refoulement. Absolute prohibition on returning individuals to places where they may face persecution, torture, or inhuman treatment. Serves as a foundational safeguard in all return practices (For details, see WP1 GAPs' Framework paper and GAPs' WP2 comparative report).

b) Human rights-based approach. Safeguards that every step of the return process respects, protects, and fulfils human rights. It emphasises treating returnees as rights-holders and states as duty-bearers. (For details, see GAPs' WP2 comparative report)

c) Vulnerability & child-centred perspective. Prioritises the needs of children when relevant and recognises differentiated impacts of return on vulnerable persons (e.g., victims of conflict, people with mental and physical health needs, etc) (For detailed discussion see GAPs' WP2 comparative report)

d) Gender responsive. Draws attention to the different risks and experiences that men, women, and gender-diverse individuals face during return and reintegration processes, and how these affect them differently (For detailed discussion, see GAPs' WP9 gender concept note).

e) Accountability. Guarantees that decision-making processes are evidence-based, open, traceable, and communicated clearly, allowing all stakeholders, especially migrants, to understand, question, and follow the actions taken at each stage (For detailed discussion see GAPs' first policy brief)

f) Do not harm. Seeks to ensure that policies or actions do not endanger migrants or exacerbate social tensions. Policies should avoid being perceived as favouring one group over another and instead aim to benefit local communities -both in host countries and return contexts- and returnees equitably (For detailed discussion see GAPs' WP4 and WP7 comparative report).

g) Migrants' Agency. Recognises migrants as active agents, not passive subjects. Best practices empower informed decision-making and participation in policymaking, particularly in voluntary or assisted return schemes (For detailed discussion, see GAPs' WP7 comparative report).

[1] Additionally, we draw inspiration from Wickramasekara, P. (2019) and the ASEAN Guidelines on Effective Return and Reintegration of Migrant Workers (2020).

[2] These include 1) Common European Asylum System (CEAS): e.g., Reception Conditions Directive 2024/1346 (Articles 5–22 on reception conditions), Return Directive (2008/115/EC, Articles 3–18 on voluntary and forced return, procedural safeguards, and detention). 2) EU Charter of Fundamental Rights: Article 4 (Prohibition of Torture), Article 18 (Right to Asylum), Article 47 (Right to an effective remedy and fair trial), and Article 19 (Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition). 3) European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR): Article 3 (Prohibition of torture or inhuman or degrading treatment), Article 8 (Right to respect for private and family life). 4) UN Convention Against Torture (UNCAT): Article 3, which prohibits returning persons to states where there are substantial grounds for believing they would be in danger of being subjected to torture.

2. CHALLENGES

Return processes are inherently complex and involve multiple actors and governance levels. Each promising practice can be associated with one or more challenges it seeks to address across different stages. The challenges presented here were identified through a systematic meta-analysis of the reports and findings produced under Work Packages 2 and 3, to organise and synthesise recurrent issues observed across policy design, implementation, and operational practice. These include:

a) Legal and Procedural. This challenge category brings together all issues related to the design, accessibility, and enforcement of return procedures. It includes whether the issuance of return decisions by authorities is timely and lawful, and how these decisions are communicated to prospective return-migrants. It also concerns respect for procedural safeguards and access to legal remedies and appeals, as well as how legal ambiguities are resolved and how inaction or delays influence procedures.

b) Identification, Detention and Case Management. This challenge category focuses on how irregularly staying individuals are identified, how their cases are processed, and how decisions regarding detention or alternatives are made. It includes examining procedures for identification and assessment, the management of individual cases, and how detention is applied, specifically whether it is proportional, legally grounded, and carried out with respect for human dignity.

c) Voluntariness and Coercion (Implementation). This challenge category addresses the continuum between voluntary and forced return. It considers how policies promote informed and supported assisted voluntary returns and whether forced returns comply with human rights and legal obligations. It also covers how risks of absconding are addressed and how different actors approach coercive techniques.

d) Governance, Cooperation and Coordination. This challenge category focuses on the organization and interaction among various stakeholders involved in the return process at local, national, regional, and even international levels. It examines how coordination and cooperation mechanisms operate, how responsibilities are distributed, and whether policies are coherent and aligned towards shared goals. Additionally, it considers how informal arrangements or "shadow" systems are managed.

e) Digital Infrastructure and Data Governance. This challenge category examines how technology and data are used to manage return processes. It considers how case management systems are adopted and implemented, how data are collected, stored, shared, and made interoperable across institutions and borders. It also explores how data protection, digital rights, transparency, and the responsible use of information are integrated into practice.

f) Institutional Capacity and Resources. This challenge category looks at the institutional and human capacity needed for effective and rights-based return systems. It encompasses topics related to institutional frameworks, staff expertise, personnel training, capacity building, funding, and resource allocation.

g) Logistics, Places, and Material Operationalisation. This challenge category explores the operational and material side of carrying out returns. It includes coordination of transport and escorts, the organisation of flights, or transfers. It also explores the conditions in detention and reception facilities.

h) Monitoring and Evaluation. This challenge category addresses how return processes are monitored, documented, and reviewed. It also examines how the reintegration into the country of return is tracked and considered in evaluating the effectiveness of policies and practices.

i) Reintegration Sustainability. This challenge category examines the post-return phase and the sustainability of reintegration in the country of origin or third country.

j) Alternatives to Return. This concerns whether there are other regularisation measures or legal pathways available as alternatives to forced return.

Both principles and challenges, even if not explicitly stated, consider participatory governance, drawing on the Global Compact for Migration's emphasis on "whole-of-government" and "whole-of-society" approaches. These practices aim to capture the inclusiveness and sustainability of governance processes.

3.RETURN STAGES

The various phases of a return policy—pre-return, return, and post-return—are inherently connected to one another. We view these as an integrated continuum, rather than fully separable.

a) **Pre-Return.** The pre-return phase occurs before the actual return takes place. This involves the initiation of the 'assisted' return or removal operation, which includes practices such as identification, provision of information, procedural safeguards, risk assessments, legal counsel, and decisions regarding detention or alternatives.

b) **Return.** This phase encompasses the physical act of removal or assisted departure, including all logistical arrangements like medical checks, escorting, travel and the use of physical enforcement measures such as pushing migrants, coercing to depart.

c) **Post-Return.** The stage after the migrant has returned to a third country (or their country of origin), which includes reintegration support and follow-up mechanisms. We view these phases as an integrated continuum, but not fully separable phases.

STRUCTURE

Based on the categories outlined above, the analysis is organised using a clear and systematic structure. It follows the three stages of return—Pre-Return, Return, and Post-Return—as the primary organising framework. Within each stage, relevant country practices are presented.

For each practice, the analysis specifies the name of the practice, actors involved, target population, implementation period, challenges addressed, and the principles explicitly or implicitly reflected. This is followed by a concise description of the practice and concludes with an assessment of benefits/impacts and shortcomings, key lessons, and general recommendations to support transferability and improvement, along with references.

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By stage

Pre-return	Return	Post-Return
Türkiye Canada Germany(i) Germany(ii) Greece (i) Jordan Netherlands Nigeria (i) Sweden (i) Sweden (ii)	Greece (ii)	Georgia Iraq Nigeria (ii) Afghanistan Morocco

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By Challenges

Legal and Procedural	Jordan Canada Greece (ii)
Identification, Detention and Case Management	Greece (i) Canada Sweden (i) Sweden (ii)
Voluntariness and Coercion	Türkiye Nigeria (i) Greece (ii)
Governance, Cooperation and Coordination	Canada Nigeria (i) Nigeria (ii) Netherlands Georgia Iraq Afghanistan
Digital Infrastructure and Data Governance	Netherlands

Institutional Capacity and Resources	Afghanistan
Logistics, Places and Material Operationalisation	Nigeria (i) Greece (i)
Monitoring and Evaluation	Netherlands Greece (ii)
Alternatives to Return	Germany (i) Germany (ii) Jordan
Reintegration Sustainability	Georgia Iraq Nigeria (ii) Morocco Afghanistan

CASES

 PRE-RETURN

 RETURN

 POST RETURN

CHAPTER 1

PRE-RETURN

Country	Practice
Türkiye	Go-and-see Visits
Canada	Immigration Detention Monitoring Programme
Germany	Duldung (Toleration Status)
Germany	Chancenaufenthaltsrecht (Opportunity Residency)
Greece	Open Centre for Migrants Registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (Urban Infrastructure)
Jordan	Livelihoods, health and legal access
Netherlands	Datafication in Dutch Return Migration Infrastructure
Nigeria	Shelter and Preparation for Return
Sweden	Prioritising supervision (uppsikt) over detention in return procedures
Sweden	Dual nonrefoulement assessment and child-centred procedures

Name of practice	Go-and-see Visits (GSVs)	
Dates	January – July 2025	
Target group	Syrians under temporary protection	
Geographic Scope	Country	Türkiye
	Regions	Asia, Europe
	Sub Region	Middle East
Main involving actor(s)	Presidency of Migration Management (PMM) UNHCR	
Return Stages	Pre return	
Challenge addressed	Voluntariness and Coercion	
Principles referred <i>(implicit or explicit)</i>	Human-Rights-Based Approach Migrants Agency	

SUMMARY

The “Go-and-see visits” (GSVs) are when potential returnees are allowed to travel temporarily to their areas of origin in Syria to assess the security situation, access to services, and general living conditions before making a final decision to return.

The visits provide the opportunity to make an informed decision and are an instrument to encourage return. From 2017 to 2022, Syrians were allowed to make GSVs to Syria during religious holidays. Since 2022, Turkish authorities have prevented Syrians who travel home from returning to Türkiye after visiting their homeland during religious holidays due to the intensifying anti-refugee sentiment in Türkiye.

From January 2025 (after the fall of Assad in Syria) to July 2025, the head of the family was allowed to enter/leave the country three times within a six-month time limit. To facilitate GSVs and permanent voluntary returns, the processing capacity of border crossings was increased from 3,000 persons a day to 15,000-20,000 persons a day.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

In May 2025, the Ministry of Interior (MoI) announced that 27,000 “pioneer immigrants” had participated in GSVs. Survey results indicated that the visits had mixed effects on the refugees’ intentions to return (UNHCR 2025). Approximately 46% of the participants felt encouraged to consider returning due to nostalgia, family ties, or hope for stability. Conversely, another 46% were deterred from returning because of harsh living conditions, lack of services, and safety concerns. Only 9% reported that their intentions had not changed. Overall, more than half (57%) of the survey respondents considered the visits helpful for making informed decisions, with 40% describing them as essential and 17% as useful (UNHCR 2025). It is estimated that the number of Syrians under temporary protection has decreased from 3.53 million in 2022 to 2.43 million as of September 2025.

However, this practice has significant limitations. There is a pressured sense of “voluntariness,” as Syrians face persistent challenges in Türkiye, such as discrimination in the labour market, unequal access to education and health services, and exposure to xenophobia, all of which may influence their decisions to return. Conditions in Syria remain precarious, characterized by ongoing insecurity, fragile governance, and limited basic services, undermining prospects for a sustainable return. Additionally, GSVs may create unrealistic expectations about the opportunities for return, rather than offering viable, long-term pathways. Finally, this model primarily serves short-term migration management goals and does not address the structural requirements necessary for a durable return, such as reconstruction and access to livelihoods in Syria.

KEY LESSONS

Information tools alone cannot determine return outcomes. GSVs can assist in making informed decisions, but they cannot fundamentally alter the overall factors affecting return. While GSVs allow individuals to assess conditions directly, the desire to return is mainly shaped by structural factors such as security, access to services, and livelihoods in the country of origin, as well as the conditions in the host country.

Voluntariness requires contextual assessment. Return decisions may reflect cumulative pressures in the host country -such as discrimination, limited access to services, and socio-economic precarity- rather than solely conditions observed in the country of origin. These parameters, including compounded vulnerabilities, need closer examination to avoid conflating informed choice with constrained decision-making.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Provide financial and reintegration support alongside monitoring. GSVs require targeted financial assistance and reintegration support for participants. These support measures should work collaboratively with independent monitoring, allowing return decisions to be assessed against different criteria.

Restore independent monitoring capacity through sustained international support. Adequate international funding is required to re-establish independent monitoring of go-and-see visits and return processes, enabling systematic observation of protection risks and longer-term outcomes.

Integrate gender- and child-sensitive considerations into visit design. Go-and-see visit frameworks should explicitly account for differentiated risks and vulnerabilities, reflecting the specific situations of women and children throughout the decision-making process.

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Name of practice	Immigration Detention Monitoring Program	
Dates	2018 - present	
Target group	Immigrants (wide group)	
Geographic Scope	Country	Canada
	Regions	Americas
	Sub Region	North America
Actor	Canadian Red Cross	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Identification, Detention and Case Management	Governance, Cooperation and Coordination
	Legal and Procedural	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Human-rights–based approach Vulnerability & Child-centred Perspective	

SUMMARY

The Canadian Red Cross (CRC) monitors the administrative detention of foreign nationals detained under the Immigration and Refugee Protection Act. Throughout the year, the CRC organises planned visits, discretionary visits or unanticipated visits in response to notifications at the Canada Border Services Agency's (CBSA) immigration holding centres, provincial jails and municipal correctional facilities. These visits monitor the treatment of detainees (by staff or other detainees); conditions of detention; ability for detainees to contact and maintain contact with family members; and legal guarantees and procedural safeguards (including access to information and interpretation services).

Teams of trained volunteers and staff, with a background in public health, social sciences or law, conduct visits to detention facilities. The CRC's visits follow a standard procedure that includes: an initial discussion with the detaining authority; a tour of detainee accommodations and facilities (kitchen, sanitary installations, healthcare facilities, dormitories, etc.); private talks with detainees, individually or as a group (if requested by detainees); and a concluding discussion with the detaining authority to discuss observations and recommendations.

The CRC holds information sessions for staff and facility personnel in direct contact with immigration detainees and convenes meetings with external stakeholders such as UNHCR, legal aid agencies, and local NGOs.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

Between 2017 and 2023, the Canadian Red Cross (CRC) visited 314 places of immigration detention and interviewed 1,467 detainees. Through its independent monitoring role, the CRC engaged detaining authorities to improve conditions of detention and promote compliance with national and international human rights standards.

Across all monitoring reports, the CRC consistently raised concerns about the comingling of immigration detainees with convicted criminal populations in provincial jails. Detaining foreign nationals for non-criminal purposes in facilities designed for criminal law enforcement was found to be incompatible with international human rights standards. The CRC therefore recommended that immigration detainees be

held in facilities other than provincial jails, or, where this is unavoidable, be strictly separated from the general prison population.

The Canada Border Services Agency (CBSA) accepted these recommendations and committed to reducing reliance on provincial jails by expanding alternatives to detention, including voice reporting, community-based case management, and electronic monitoring, as well as by increasing transfers to immigration holding centres. As a result, the number of immigration detainees held in provincial jails decreased from 2,043 in 2016–2017 to 931 in 2022–2023.

Despite this progress, the CBSA continues to use provincial jails for the detention of individuals assessed as higher risk and in regions where dedicated immigration holding centres are not available

KEY LESSONS

Independent detention monitoring can drive measurable policy change. Regular, structured monitoring by independent humanitarian actors can influence detention policy and practice by identifying systemic shortcomings and sustaining dialogue with authorities. In Canada, the CRC’s monitoring programme contributed to CBSA’s decision to expand alternatives to detention and reduce reliance on provincial jails.

The use of criminal detention facilities for administrative immigration detention raises significant protection concerns. Housing immigration detainees alongside convicted criminal populations risks blurring the non-punitive nature of administrative detention and may conflict with international human rights standards. In Canada, CRC monitoring visits consistently identified this issue, leading to recommendations to limit the use of provincial jails for immigration detention and, where unavoidable, to apply strict separation measures.

Policy commitments to reduce detention require structural capacity to be fully realised. Even where authorities accept monitoring recommendations, implementation may remain partial if suitable infrastructure and alternatives are unevenly available. In Canada, despite a significant reduction in numbers, the CBSA continues to rely on provincial jails for higher-risk cases and in regions without dedicated immigration holding centres

RECOMMENDATIONS

Independent detention monitoring must be accompanied by systematic follow-up and accountability mechanisms. Monitoring loses effectiveness if findings are not translated into measurable implementation and review processes. In Canada, this would mean establishing a formal mechanism to track, assess, and publicly report on how the Canada Border Services Agency implements recommendations issued by the Canadian Red Cross

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Name of practice	Duldung	
Dates	Toleration for employment 1 Jan 2020 Toleration for training was first implemented in 2016	
Target group	Immigrants (wide group)	
Geographic Scope	Country	Germany
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	North Europe
Actor(s)	Federal Employment Agency Foreign Authorities	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Alternatives to Return	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Human-rights–based approach Do-no-harm	

SUMMARY

The “Duldung” is a toleration of stay for persons with an order to leave the country under the German Residence Act (Sec. 60a). Deportation of the migrant is suspended for a defined period (usually 3-6 months), but this is not equivalent to a regular status, as the so-called ‘obligation to leave the country’ remains effective, leaving the migrants in a “limbo” status (Ince-Beqo, 2024; Schurade et al., 2025). Deportation may be temporarily suspended on urgent humanitarian, personal, or public interest grounds.

There are several forms of toleration linked to employment or training.

(i) The *Ausbildungsduldung* (Sec. 60c Residence Act) applies to persons enrolled in a vocational training programme; deportation is suspended for the duration of the training, and upon successful completion and securing employment in the trained profession, a two-year residence permit may be granted.

(ii) The *Beschäftigungsduldung* (Sec. 60d Residence Act) is available to those who have been lawfully employed for at least 12 months and meet further statutory conditions, including a basic spoken command of the German language. Holders of this form of toleration are protected from deportation, and the status may be extended to certain family members under defined conditions and can provide a pathway to a residence permit after 30 months.

The Duldung “light” (Sec. 60b Residence Act) applies when deportation is suspended due to the individual’s failure to cooperate in establishing identity; it entails additional restrictions, including a work prohibition and exclusion from pathways linked to training or employment

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

In 2025, 185,868 persons were tolerated in Germany, 39,642 were issued this “status” in 2025 for the first time; however, 105,162 resided in Germany for three or more years and 58,958 even for six or more years (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b, p. 30).

The concept of toleration is often viewed as a potentially promising practice (Hendow & Qaisrani, 2024, pp. 52 et seq.; Catelli and Levoy, 2025, p. 4), but it does have its flaws. This temporary status allows migrants to stay legally in Germany and provides them with access to certain social and welfare rights. The German government has established comprehensive regulations regarding toleration, offering this temporary residency to individuals in various situations, more so than many other EU countries. By providing these regulations, the government ensures that migrants are not left unsupported after their asylum applications are rejected, allowing them the possibility of regular residence.

Migrants are required to renew their toleration status at regular intervals for as long as it remains in effect. This situation places them in a de facto limbo, restricting their ability to settle in Germany due to the non-permanent nature of this status. Depending on the specific type of toleration, the renewal may be needed every few months. This often results in a "chain of toleration" (Kettenduldung), which allows migrants to extend their stay in Germany, but with limited rights. The grounds for extending toleration are reassessed regularly and are influenced by political developments in the country of origin as well as domestic electoral and immigration policy. Some civil society organizations advocate for the issuance of formal residence permits to help migrants move beyond the toleration status (Hendow & Qaisrani, 2024, p. 53).

KEY LESSONS

Intermediate forms of toleration create complex legal categories. Across contexts, the use of multiple interim statuses between lawful residence and return can generate administrative complexity and inconsistent rights regimes. In Germany, several distinct forms of toleration exist, making it the European country with the largest number and broadest range of "tolerated" foreigners. This illustrates how extensive categorisation can complicate both governance and migrants' pathways out of temporary status.

Prolonged toleration can entrench a structural limbo. Where toleration becomes the default solution for individuals with a pending or unenforceable return, it risks producing long-term uncertainty. This situation limits access to services, inhibits integration planning, and constrains participation in socio-economic life. The German case shows how toleration, although granting a lawful stay, can still deprive individuals of a tangible integration perspective when renewal is uncertain, and rights remain restricted.

Toleration can function as an open-ended mechanism of limited rights. In any system where temporary stay is repeatedly renewed without offering a credible pathway to regularisation or return, toleration may operate as a de facto form of prolonged disenfranchisement. Research on Germany (e.g. Schütze, 2025) highlights how toleration can become temporally indeterminate, underscoring the need for safeguards that prevent indefinite reliance on exceptional measures.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Establish clear legal pathways out of prolonged toleration. States should consider mechanisms that enable individuals with long-term toleration statuses to transition into more secure residence permits, thereby reducing dependence on repeated short-term extensions and supporting greater stability and integration. In the case of Germany, the Opportunity Residence Permit (Chancenaufenthalt), explained below, illustrates an approach that offers a structured route for tolerated foreigners to move out of cycles of repeated "Duldung" renewals, provided they meet defined criteria.

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Name of practice	Chancenaufenthaltsrecht (Opportunity Residency)	
Dates	Entered into force on 31.12.2022, ended on 31.12.2025	
Target group	Possible return migrants (General)	
Geographic Scope	Country	Germany
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	North Europe
Actor(s)	Foreign Authorities	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Alternatives to Return	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Human-rights–based approach Migrants’ Agency	

SUMMARY

The Opportunity Residence Right (Sec. 104c Residence Act) provides an 18-month residence permit for individuals holding a temporary toleration status, allowing them to transition toward a long-term legal residence permit. It is non-renewable, and during this limited period, holders are given the chance to acquire the necessary requirements for a long-term residence permit. The beneficiaries are not required to prove identity or income security, which lowers the barrier to switching.

The instrument aims to bridge the gap between “Duldung” and a long-term residency by incentivising the clarification of identity and integration into the labour market. Given that Duldung is characterised by uncertainty and restrictions that impede long-term integration, the Opportunity Residence Right aims to reduce the number of persons trapped in the “Duldung” status and prevent the return of individuals who are sufficiently integrated once their identity has been clarified.

Those eligible are individuals who have held a toleration permit (“Duldung” and “Duldung light”) for at least five years, independently of nationality or origin. The status includes unrestricted access to employment, access to language courses, and can be extended to spouses and unmarried minor children. However, the “Opportunity Residence Right” can only be issued if the person has continuously resided in Germany for five years by 30 October 2022. As a result, it does not offer a pathway for individuals who will enter Duldung status in the future.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

By mid-2025, 226,506 people in Germany were under an obligation to leave, of whom 184,988 were tolerated (~80%) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a, p. 35). This represents a decline from 248,145 tolerated individuals at the end of 2022, before the Opportunity Residence Right was introduced, with the reduction attributed both to the programme and to an increase in deportations.

As of May 2025, 84,106 people had received the Opportunity Residence Right. Of these, 16,646 had successfully transitioned to a long-term residence permit (~19%), while 31,372 remained within the 18-month grant period (~37%) (Mediendienst Integration, 2025).

This contrasts with the figures estimated at the start of the programme, which suggested that 137,000 tolerated migrants had lived in Germany for more than five years and were eligible to apply (Peitz, 2025, p. 2).

Despite the benefits, only a small percentage of grantees manage to complete the transition within 18 months —namely less than one-fifth of the total 84,106 grantees. One significant challenge for these grantees is the requirement to clarify their identity within this timeframe. Migrants who cannot provide proof of identity— often due to a lack of cooperation from authorities in their country of origin or other circumstances beyond their control—must address this issue to become eligible for a long-term residence permit. Additionally, grantees who have not previously fulfilled integration requirements often find it difficult to meet all obligations at once. These obligations include learning German, attending the required integration course, passing the “Life in Germany” test, and securing stable employment to ensure long-term financial stability. The cut-off date rule (October 31, 2017) further limits eligibility, excluding many long-term tolerated migrants. Critics advocate for a more flexible, criteria-based approach that considers length of stay, progress in integration, and willingness to cooperate.

Political debate over the programme is divided. Some actors advocate easing requirements to increase successful transitions, while others—including far-right parties and members of the governing coalition— oppose it, citing risks of granting residence to individuals with unclear or falsified identity. The 2025 coalition agreement contains provisions for a new temporary residence right with stricter eligibility and employment criteria.

KEY LESSONS

Regularisation may offer a credible exit from the precarious and temporary status of migrants. The *Chancenaufenthaltsrecht* has shown that regularization can provide a viable path out of long-term and chained tolerance status. Its design, particularly the opportunity for beneficiaries to participate in full integration activities over 18 months, is widely recognized as a positive innovation. This approach fosters cooperation, minimizes administrative disputes, and allows migrants to focus on their integration. Additionally, the program has facilitated better access to the labor market for participants, which has helped reduce dependence on the social security system.

Lowering procedural barriers can improve cooperation and enable meaningful integration. Regularisation mechanisms that permit applicants to participate in integration measures without having to meet certain requirements— often challenging due to factors beyond the migrant’s control, such as proving income security, language proficiency, or identity documentation— enable migrants and authorities to engage in a more constructive and solutions-oriented manner.

Time-limited or narrowly defined eligibility rules restrict the systemic impact of regularisation programmes. Instruments for regularisation that depend on strict cut-off dates or narrow eligibility windows risk benefiting only a small portion of the population that has been tolerated. Without ongoing or flexible criteria, these measures may not effectively address the structural persistence of chain toleration and its related uncertainties. The implementation of strict cut-off dates and short application windows has significantly reduced the number of beneficiaries. With the current coalition planning to phase out the *Chancenaufenthaltsrecht* and replace it with an even more restrictive and similarly time-bound mechanism, chain toleration is expected to remain a central aspect of Germany’s migration governance. This approach continues to maintain a system that offers limited rights while allowing for the potential removal of the affected foreigners.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Extend access to regularisation programmes to reduce long-term uncertainty. Regularisation programmes are more effective when eligibility is broad, flexible, and not limited by arbitrary cut-off dates. In Germany, this would mean extending the *Chancenaufenthaltsrecht* beyond 1 January 2026 and avoiding replacement by a mechanism with higher entry hurdles. The cut-off date for eligibility should be abolished, enabling any foreigner who has lived in Germany for five years to apply for the 18-month grant on a rolling basis.

Recognise genuine efforts to clarify identity and integrate. Regularization programs should consider obstacles that are beyond the migrant’s control, such as difficulties in obtaining identity documentation from their home countries. Allowing more time for identity verification and recognizing the efforts made toward integration during the grant period would enhance the chances of a successful transition to regular residency.

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Name of practice	Open Centre for Migrants Registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration	
Dates	2015 - present	
Target group	Potential Returnees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Greece
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	Mediterranean
Actor	International Organization for Migration Reception and Identification Service (Ministry of Migration and Asylum)	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Logistics, Places, and Materiality Identification, Detention and Case Management.	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Human-rights–based approach	

SUMMARY

The Open Centre for Migrants Registered for AVRR (OCAVRR) in Athens has emerged as a notable example of an urban, temporary accommodation facility for migrants registered in the AVRR programme run by IOM Greece. Established in 2015 in collaboration with the Reception and Identification Service of the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, OCAVRR has a capacity of approximately 100 residents. It accommodates vulnerable AVRR participants either throughout the return process or during specific stages. Unlike the prevailing reliance on detention for all RMs, OCAVRR functions as an open facility, providing social, medical, psycho-educational and recreational services.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

Between September 2019 and August 2023, the centre hosted 2,482 migrants in total, while the current AVRR programme (September 2023-December 2027) aims to accommodate 1,700 individuals.

OCAVRR, as the most well-organised urban facility for returnees in Greece, stands in sharp contrast to the absence of comparable urban structures dedicated to asylum seekers and beneficiaries of protection. This disparity raises critical concerns regarding the state's priorities, suggesting a greater commitment to ensuring dignified living conditions for those who consent to return to their countries of origin than for those in need of protection and integration into the local society.

KEY LESSONS

Open urban accommodation facilities are essential for a dignified and rights-compliant solution. Contrary to the conditions prevailing in detention facilities and in spatially isolated camp-like accommodation centres, open urban accommodation facilities for returnees can ensure a more dignified process and living conditions during the pre-return phase.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Separate voluntary return programmes from detention. AVRR programmes should opt for genuinely voluntary participation. Individuals already registered in the programme should not be detained and should be offered supportive accommodation instead. In Greece, authorities could ensure this by offering placement at OCAVRR.

Improve reception and accommodation for all migrants. Humane reception conditions should extend beyond returnees to asylum seekers and beneficiaries of protection. Urban facilities that offer safe and dignified living spaces are more effective than isolated camps for supporting well-being and integration. In Greece, OCAVRR serves as a model for such facilities, demonstrating how urban accommodation can provide dignified living spaces for its residents.

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Name of practice	Livelihoods, health, and legal access	
Dates	2014 - present	
Target group	Syrian Refugees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Jordan
	Regions	Asia
	Sub Region	Middle-East
Actor	Non-Governmental Organisations	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Legal and Procedural Alternatives to Return	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Non-refoulement. Human rights-based approach Gender responsive Vulnerability & Child-centred perspective	

SUMMARY

The EU Madad Fund (EU Regional Trust Fund in Response to the Syrian Crisis), started in 2014, has assisted Syrian refugees and local communities by improving access to education, employment, healthcare, clean water, and protection services. It aims to create strong and cohesive communities, with a particular focus on children, youth, and women. The Madad Fund has also supported women's access to job training and helped establish women-led businesses, including beauty salons, restaurants, and retail shops, especially since many refugee households are headed by women. Then, the Jordan Compact (2016) allowed Syrian refugees to get work permits in specific sectors such as agriculture, construction, and manufacturing. While the Jordan Compact and Madad Fund incorporate gender-sensitive elements, their gender responsiveness remains uneven and highly dependent on complementary services such as childcare, transport, and legal support.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

In terms of impact, work permits provide formal recognition and some benefits, including reduced risk of arrest, improved working conditions, and, in some cases, access to social security, though many refugees working informally see limited incentive to formalise due to administrative costs. Skills gained through vocational training, cash-for-work, and small business initiatives, alongside work experience and social networks, strengthen refugees' human capital, supporting potential sustainable return to Syria or durable local integration. However, evidence on long-term effects on actual return trajectories remains limited.

This policy measure/practice has also shortcomings. The Jordan Compact has fallen short in meeting its job creation goals. Although the plan aimed to create 200,000 jobs for Syrians, by 2018 only about 120,000 work permits had been issued, and just 42,000 permit-holders found formal employment. This disparity illustrates the gap between the policy's objectives and the realities of the labour market. Most work permits are concentrated in low-paying and seasonal sectors, particularly agriculture, and are often located far from refugee communities.

The geographic distance, along with challenges such as transportation and childcare, particularly affects women's ability to take advantage of these opportunities. Significant gaps also persist in legal protection and civil documentation. Many refugees—particularly those in informal settlements or with complex cases, such as unregistered marriages or children born in displacement—face barriers to obtaining or correcting official documents, creating inter-generational risks of statelessness and limiting both local integration and future return. Conditionalities, fines, and cross-border documentation requirements further hinder access, requiring ongoing advocacy to prevent the imposition of unaffordable penalties.

KEY LESSONS

Rights-based labour market access requires realistic sectoral planning. Granting work permits is a precondition for self-reliance, but without investment in sectors where the host country has a comparative advantage, employment targets may not be met.

Programme design must align with refugees' realities, particularly for women. Access barriers such as childcare, transport, safety concerns, and social norms limit participation, even where permits and training exist. In Za'atari, women hold only 20% of active work permits, underscoring the need for practical gender-sensitive measures.

Integrated services and legal support strengthen resilience but need explicit links to return. Multi-sectoral investments in education, health, livelihoods, and protection enhance human capital and community systems. However, connections to future return scenarios—portable qualifications, recognition of learning, and civil documentation—remain weak. Legal assistance is essential for a safe and dignified return.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Link labour-market access to genuine economic opportunities. Work permits should be tied to sectors with real comparative advantage and demand, supported by active labour-market policies, private-sector incentives, and local industrial strategies, rather than focusing solely on permit numbers.

Integrate legal aid and civil documentation into self-reliance and return programming. Civil documentation, residency regularisation, and legal counselling must be core components, with coordination between host- and origin-country authorities to ensure recognition of documents upon return.

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Name of practice	Datafication in Dutch Return Migration Infrastructure	
Dates	2020-2024	
Target group	Future Returnees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Netherlands
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	North Europe
Actor(s)	Dutch Repatriation and Departure Agency (DTenV)	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Governance, Cooperation and Coordination Monitoring and Evaluation Digital Infrastructure and Data Governance	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Accountability	

SUMMARY

Within the wider chain of government agencies governing migration—under the responsibility of the Ministry of Security and Justice (known as the Vreemdelingenketen)—there is a specialized state departure agency involved in return processes (Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek / DTenV). This agency collaborates directly and indirectly (through funding schemes) with partners such as the IOM, the Dutch Refugee Council, and other NGOs. A network of interconnected systems (SIGMA) enables data sharing between government agencies, including the Immigration Authorities (IND), the Central Agency for the Reception of Asylum Seekers (COA), the Immigration Police, the Identification and Human Trafficking unit (AVIM), and the Repatriation and Departure Agency (DTenV).

Each agency also operates its own tools: the Dutch Repatriation and Departure Agency (DTenV) relies mainly on ISTV (Return and Departure Information System), as all relevant information for DTenV case workers appears in ISTV (from the first AVIM hearing to EURODAC information).

Information of all kinds is linked through a migrant's unique V-number. This identifier is the key to unlocking a migrant's entire data trail, used not just by authorities but also by lawyers and advocacy groups. Meanwhile, systems like EUVIS (EU Visa System) and Frontex's RIAT (Reintegration Assistance Tool) extend this datafication beyond borders, capturing visa applicants' details -even those rejected-leaving lasting digital traces.

For migration officers, these tools are indispensable. They provide instant access to critical information, including health records, criminal history, and legal representation, across agencies like COA, KMar, and DJI.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

The Dutch migration system faces critical shortcomings in data sharing due to strict privacy regulations and role-based access barriers. Agencies like COA (asylum support) and DTenV (return agency) are legally restricted from sharing digital records-such as case manager reports or sensitive health data. This fragmentation

directs agencies to rely on informal workarounds, like verbal exchanges in meetings or hiring intermediaries (e.g., nurses) to access protected information, undermining transparency and accountability. These verbal exchanges are within legal practices but remain largely unknown to migrants.

A second major issue is the blurring of boundaries between care and control, particularly for NGOs. Programmes like the LVV (pilot programme on sheltering and return of undocumented migrants / 2020-2025) require NGOs to monitor migrants' return processes while providing support, turning them into de facto extensions of state surveillance. Systems like the Clientvolgsysteem (CVS) record and track migrants' details, but NGOs selectively share data with authorities, creating ethical dilemmas and practices of contestation. Migrants, meanwhile, are often unaware of how their data circulates, leaving them vulnerable to unintended surveillance and procedural unfairness.

KEY LESSONS

Standardisation vs local context. Harmonising migration data enables policymakers to identify trends and develop evidence-based, strategic interventions at scale. However, standardisation risks overlooking local realities and complexities, leading to policies that are less responsive to the actual needs and experiences of migrants on the ground.

Efficiency vs marginalisation. Digital systems, biometrics, and data infrastructures improve efficiency, monitoring, and enforcement of migration processes, fostering collaboration among stakeholders. Conversely, these systems can fragment data, reinforce top-down control, and marginalise migrants' voices, creating a surveillance-oriented approach that prioritises state and institutional agendas over individual rights and perspectives

Collaboration vs power imbalances. Expanding data-sharing platforms and collaborations support coordinated governance and legitimise policies through evidence-based decision-making. Nonetheless, these infrastructures may obscure power dynamics, reinforce hierarchies, and exclude migrants' lived realities, as data often reflects the priorities of states and organisations rather than those of migrants or local communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Standardise with flexibility and transparency. Establish consistent definitions and methodologies across datasets to improve data quality, comparability, and reliability. However, allow for flexibility to adapt to local contexts and ensure transparency by clearly documenting data sources, methodologies, and limitations. This balance builds trust, supports critical analysis, and prevents the reinforcement of top-down narratives.

Collaborate critically and equitably. Foster multi-actor collaboration among governments, NGOs, and migrants, while implementing oversight mechanisms to prevent data misuse and ensure equitable governance. Prioritise partnerships that empower migrants and local communities and critically assess power dynamics to avoid reinforcing hierarchies or excluding key stakeholders.

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Name of practice	Shelter and Preparation for Return Information Campaigns on Assisted Voluntary Return	
Dates	2010 - present	
Target group	Returnees (inside and outside Nigeria)	
Geographic Scope	Country	Nigeria
	Regions	Africa
	Sub Region	West Africa
Actor	Patriotic Citizen Initiatives	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Logistics, Places, and Materiality. Governance, Cooperation and Coordination Voluntariness and Coercion	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Human-rights-based approach Vulnerability & Child-centred perspective Migrants' Agency	

SUMMARY

The Patriotic Citizen Initiatives (PCI) has provided assistance to migrants who have been rescued from prisons in Libya, as well as those mistakenly identified as Nigerians when they are actually from countries like Sierra Leone, Mali, and Senegal. In partnership with the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), PCI offers temporary shelter for up to three months while the migrants' documentation and return arrangements are processed. Additionally, PCI has hosted Congolese nationals who were trafficked into Nigeria, helping them prepare for a safe and dignified return to the Democratic Republic of Congo.

PCI also serves as a local partner of the European Reintegration Support Organisation (ERSO). Their representatives travel to the Netherlands to reach out to irregular migrants—including those in deportation camps—informing them about the benefits of Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR). They also participate in high-level European engagement to promote dignified, informed, and sustainable return and reintegration for Nigerian migrants. By filling the information gap, PCI helps migrants make informed choices about AVR as an alternative to forced return. Beyond receiving them, PCI arranged temporary accommodation, retrieved belongings sent from Europe, and supported returnees in mapping out the gradual disbursement of reintegration assistance.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

PCI supports the dignified return and reintegration of migrants, assisting Nigerians from Europe and Libya as well as non-Nigerians who were misidentified or trafficked. In partnership with IOM, it provides temporary shelter and documentation support, while with ERSO it informs irregular migrants about Assisted Voluntary Return. Through EU engagement, PCI fosters collaboration and best practices, and also helps returnees with accommodation, belongings, and reintegration planning, bridging pre- and post-return stages. Despite these efforts, its reach is limited, shelter is short-term, documentation is slow, geographic scope is narrow, and sustainability is uncertain due to reliance on donor funding.

KEY LESSONS

PCI's experience shows that reintegration must be holistic, combining shelter, documentation, counselling, and financial support to ensure dignity and continuity.

Partnerships with IOM, ERSO and EU engagement extend its reach, while information on AVR empowers migrants to make informed choices. Its adaptability in assisting non-Nigerians is notable, but challenges remain—limited scale, donor dependence, short-term shelter, bureaucratic delays, and narrow geographic focus. Overall, PCI highlights the need for comprehensive, collaborative, and sustainable reintegration approaches.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Initiatives and NGOs like PCI should expand their operations with sustainable funding and stronger institutional capacity to reduce reliance on partners. Shelter should extend beyond three months, with added psychosocial, vocational, and livelihood support, while streamlined documentation with agencies like NAPTIP, NIMC, and NCFRMI would ease delays.

Geographic coverage must go beyond Nigeria, the Netherlands, and Denmark, and advocacy on AVR should be strengthened. Deeper EU engagement can foster collaboration and best practices, while robust monitoring and evaluation will improve design, demonstrate impact, and enhance credibility.

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Name of practice	Prioritising supervision (uppsikt) over detention in return procedures	
Dates	(No Information)	
Target group	Future-return migrants / migrants with return decisions	
Geographic Scope	Country	Sweden
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	North Europe, Scandinavia
Actor	Swedish Migration Agency Migration Courts and the Migration Court of Appeal Police Authority	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Identification, Detention, and Case Management	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Human-rights–based approach	

SUMMARY

Swedish law embeds a “supervision first” model: under the Aliens Act, authorities must consider supervision (*uppsikt* in Swedish) before resorting to detention, and deprivation of liberty is only lawful when less intrusive measures are insufficient. Uppsikt allows people with return decisions to remain in the community under conditions such as periodic reporting to the Police or the Swedish Migration Agency and, in some cases, surrendering travel documents, thereby maintaining contact and compliance without confinement. In principle, this model aligns with the EU Return Directive’s requirement to prioritise alternatives to detention and, when implemented, offers a less intrusive and generally lowercost option for both migrants and authorities.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

On paper, the “supervision first” framework is a good practice, because it requires explicit consideration of noncustodial measures before detention is imposed as well as it enables case management that can support compliance while protecting family life and mental health and reducing costs relative to detention.

In practice, however, detention is used more often than the legal model would suggest, and supervision remains underutilised. For example, in 2024 the number of detainees held under the Aliens Act increased from 3,084 in 2023 to 3,695 in 2024 (Swedish Migration Agency, Annual Report 2024, Ref. no. 1.3.2-2025-1844). By contrast, in 2024 the Migration Agency issued only 217 supervision (*uppsikt*) decisions, up from 155 in 2023 (AIDA, Sweden Country Report – Update 2024). Thus, in 2024 supervision decisions represented roughly 5.55% of all return decisions, clearly indicating that supervision is underutilised.

Oversight bodies and NGOs, including the Parliamentary Ombudsman and the National Audit Office, have criticised it on three grounds: 1) weak or missing reasoning as to why supervision is not used instead of detention; 2) insufficient, qualitative proportionality assessments, and 3) lack of clear guidance on when and how *uppsikt* should be preferred.

In a newly published report the Swedish National Audit Office (December 2025, Detention in the migration process – *A costly measure without clear governance* - RiR 2025:32) has examined whether the Swedish Migration Agency's and the Swedish Police Authority's work with detention facilities is effective, and concluded that detention operations are not effective. "Processes at the Swedish Migration Agency and the Swedish Police Authority do not ensure effective decisions on who is to be detained, cooperation between the agencies is deficient and the Swedish Migration Agency does not ensure legally certain and cost-effective operation of the detention centres".

KEY LESSONS

Monitoring and enforcement prevent detention as default. Legal safeguards such as proportionality clauses and formal alternatives (*uppsikt*) must be backed by monitoring and enforcement; otherwise, detention risks becoming the default.

Transparency in statistics ensures the supervision first practice. Transparent statistics on how many people are detained versus placed under supervision are essential to assess whether the "supervision first" principle is applied in practice.

Non-custodial options must be the rule. Clear, case by case reasoning is needed to justify any departure from the non-custodial option.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Mandate rigorous, case-by-case justification for all detention decisions. Operationalise proportionality in detention decisions through strict, individualised reasoning in every detention decision, explicitly documenting why *uppsikt* or other alternatives are not sufficient, and ensure rapid, effective judicial review and effective judicial oversight.

Scale up and diversify alternatives to detention beyond basic reporting obligations. Case-management models, community-based hosting, and financial or other guarantees should be developed to avoid overreliance on a binary choice between detention and a single alternative.

Strengthen independent monitoring and transparency. Publish regular public reporting on detention conditions, use of alternatives such as supervision, and return outcomes, and empower independent monitoring bodies to review proportionality and the use of alternatives systematically.

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Name of practice	Dual non refoulement assessment and child-centred procedures	
Dates	(No Information)	
Target group	Future-return migrants / migrants with return decisions	
Geographic Scope	Country	Sweden
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	North Europe, Scandinavia
Actor	Swedish Migration Agency Migration Courts and the Migration Court of Appeal Police Authority	
Return Stages	Pre-Return	
Challenge addressed	Identification, Detention, and Case Management	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Non-refoulement Vulnerability & Child-centred perspective Human-rights-based approach	

SUMMARY

1) Dual assessment of non-refoulement: Sweden operates a dual assessment of the nonrefoulement principle: first during the asylum procedure, where the Migration Agency and, on appeal, the Migration Courts examine risks of persecution or serious harm under the Aliens Act and the Refugee/Qualification Directive, and again after a return decision through enforcement stage control of “impediments to enforcement” under Chapter 12 of the Aliens Act (especially Sections 1–3a and 18–19), where new or newly invoked circumstances can trigger a residence permit or reexamination before removal is carried out (AIDA Sweden Country Report, 2025). This twostep structure offers stronger safeguards than in many EU Member States, which typically conduct only a single, pre-decision assessment. Although it can create some procedural duplication, it reinforces protection against breaches of Article 3 ECHR, as illustrated by numerous second stage decisions suspending or altering removals. In 2024, 517 decisions were taken under Chapter 12 Section 18 on impediments to enforcement, of which 491 resulted in residence permits, mostly on “other special grounds” or changed circumstances rather than classic asylum grounds (AIDA Sweden Country Report, 2025, p. 60).

2) Best interests of the child (BIC) and unaccompanied minors (UAM): The Swedish Migration Agency has a central responsibility to ensure that the best interests of the child (BIC) are a primary consideration throughout the asylum and return process, in coordination with legal guardians, Migration Courts, and municipal child protection authorities. For UAMs who cannot be returned in practice or who have strong humanitarian grounds, Sweden may grant temporary residence permits, which can be renewed and, in some cases, provide protection and relative stability up to the age of 18; however, such permits are subject to individual assessment, increasingly restrictive rules, and do not constitute an automatic right.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

Dual assessments of nonrefoulement function as an additional safety net, with hundreds of impediments to enforcement decisions each year that can halt removals or lead to residence permits when new risks or circumstances arise.

In principle, systematic consideration of the BIC, together with the possibility of temporary, renewable permits for nonreturnable UAMs, can provide child specific protection, continuity, and some stability during crucial developmental periods, even when return remains the long-term policy goal.

However, these practices have notable shortcomings. The strict “new circumstances” requirement for subsequent applications and impediments to enforcement claims can limit protection in practice, as late emerging or poorly documented risks may be filtered out despite their seriousness. Internal and external reviews also point to persistent gaps in identifying and weighing children’s interests and asylum grounds, indicating that BIC obligations are sometimes treated as formalities rather than truly guiding decisions. This raises concerns that the potential of both the dual nonrefoulement system and the child centred framework is not fully realised in day-to-day practice.

KEY LESSONS

Dual stage protection screening can significantly strengthen compliance with non-refoulement, especially when safeguards extend beyond the initial asylum decision and remain available up to the point of removal. Sweden’s impediments to enforcement procedure shows how a second review can, in practice, prevent removals where new risks or country of origin changes emerge.

Specialised child protection assessments require external checks. Concentrating BIC determinations in migration authorities can improve internal consistency but needs complementary oversight to address blind spots and structural biases. Swedish case law reviews, ombudsman reports, and research repeatedly highlight weaknesses in how children’s interests are documented, analysed, and balanced, underscoring the role of courts, ombuds institutions, and NGOs in reinforcing child rights-compliant decision-making.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Consolidate and generalise post-decision protection safeguards. States should establish clear impediments to enforcement procedures with automatic suspensive effect, so that removal is halted whenever new protection-relevant elements arise, ensuring full, up to date consideration of nonrefoulement risks before enforcement.

Institutionalise a genuinely child-centred, rights-based approach. This requires detailed BIC guidelines, trained child specialist caseworkers, early and routine involvement of child protection services, and guarantees that children’s own protection grounds are examined independently from adult family members’ cases, with decisions clearly documenting how BIC considerations shaped the outcome.

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CHAPTER 2

RETURN

Country	Practice
Greece	Counter-practices of documentation and contestation

Name of practice	Counter-practices of documentation and contestation against forced returns	
Dates	2023	
Target group	Future returnees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Greece
	Regions	Europe
	Sub Region	Balkans
Actor(s)	Greek National Commission for Human Rights Greek Council for Refugees	
Return Stages	Return	
Challenge addressed	Monitoring and Evaluation Voluntariness and Coercion Legal and Procedural	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Non-refoulement Do no-harm	

SUMMARY

The Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns (pushbacks) is an independent network formed under the Greek National Commission for Human Rights (GNCHR). The Mechanism constitutes a synergy between the GNCHR and twelve civil society organisations active in providing legal, medical, psychosocial, and other services to third-country nationals, with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) contributing expertise and technical support as a cooperating agency. The Recording Mechanism monitors and reports incidents of informal forced returns from Greece to other countries, to promote compliance with the principle of non-refoulement and safeguard procedural guarantees.

The second counter-practice against pushbacks, the submission of applications for interim measures to the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) by legal NGOs, has emerged as a promising strategy to protect migrants at risk. Interim measures, or 'Rule 39 orders,' are urgent orders issued by the ECtHR under 'exceptional circumstances', when applicants face an imminent threat of serious and irreparable harm. Once indicated, these measures are legally binding on the relevant state, which is obliged to comply.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

By adopting a standardized, transparent, and scientific methodology, the Recording Mechanism enhances the credibility of reported incidents. It is recognized as a promising practice due to the lack of any other official and effective system for recording pushbacks. Additionally, it establishes a vital network that connects previously fragmented efforts by various organizations that had operated independently.

According to the Greek Council for Refugees, between March 2022 and June 2025, the organization represented 1,189 refugees from different countries before the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR). They submitted 111 applications for interim measures to secure humanitarian assistance and access to the asylum process. The Court granted the requested interim measures in all cases, ordering the Greek government not to remove the refugees from the country and, in most cases, to provide them with food, water, and proper medical care.

KEY LESSONS

Coordinated action is needed to document human rights violations. Collaboration among NGOs, advisory bodies, and international organisations is essential to guarantee that abuses are properly recorded and followed up on. Coordination between GNCHR, legal NGOs and other civil society partners has been key to systematically tracking and documenting pushbacks, collecting evidence, and supporting follow-up actions.

Counter-practices are critical even in the face of official denial. Independent monitoring and legal contestation remain crucial tools to uphold human rights when state authorities deny or underreport violations. The Greek experience shows that mechanisms such as recording systems and ECtHR interim measure applications can expose violations, safeguard non-refoulement, and ensure that affected individuals receive basic rights and protection despite systemic obstacles.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Immediately halt pushbacks. States must cease all forced or informal returns to uphold human rights, protect vulnerable populations, and comply with the principle of non-refoulement.

Strengthen coordinated documentation and reporting. Collaboration among international organisations, NGOs, and advisory bodies is essential to systematically record, monitor, and report pushbacks, enabling evidence-based advocacy and legal interventions to protect affected migrants.

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CHAPTER 3

POST RETURN

Country	Practice
Georgia	Reintegration Programme
Iraq	National Referral Mechanism
Nigeria	Post-return policies (several)
Afghanistan	High Commission on Return Migration
Morocco	National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum

Name of practice	Reintegration programs	
Dates	(No Information)	
Target group	Returnees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Georgia
	Regions	Asia, Europe
	Sub Region	South Caucasus
Actor	Ministry of Interior Ministry of Labour, Health and Social Affairs Frontex. International and local NGOs	
Return Stages	Post-Return	
Challenge addressed	Reintegration Sustainability	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Migrants' Agency	

SUMMARY

To improve official reintegration programs, especially during the initial phase of return, Georgian state authorities seek to utilise extensive social networks, to reduce costs and redirect more resources to other support initiatives. Involving local actors with contextual knowledge is crucial for developing effective solutions. Frontex collaborates with local NGOs to create customized solutions for returnees.

1) *Assistance in business plan development.* Returnees who have spent extended periods abroad often lack up-to-date knowledge of local market conditions. Local NGOs provide context-specific guidance and assist beneficiaries in preparing a realistic and feasible business plan. Implementing agencies are also required to monitor the further development of supported businesses, typically one to two years after establishment.

2) *Procurement of goods instead of cash assistance.* Rather than disbursing funds directly, implementing partners supply beneficiaries with in-kind products needed to establish their businesses. This approach limits overpricing and reduces the risk of misallocation.

3) *Assistance with medical issues.* In Georgia, the national health service does not fully cover the costs of medical treatments. Therefore, the possibility of receiving assistance with medical issues is a good practice concerning both the well-being of a returnee and the efficiency of the entire system.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

The benefits of reintegration programs in Georgia are threefold. First, for returnees, these programs provide the opportunity to gain independence and reduce reliance on social benefits by starting their own businesses. Second, the Georgian government benefits by fostering economic development and lessening the burden on the social security system. Lastly, for the EU, these programs help minimize the risk of returnees re-emigrating and promotes the EU as a solid and reliable partner.

In 2018, there were 815 beneficiaries of reintegration programmes in Georgia, compared with 6,625 total returns. Most assistance targeted returnees from EU Member States, with income-generating project grants being the most common form of support. Also, the programmes have contributed to strengthening mutual trust between the EU and the Georgian state, which could potentially lead to improved cooperation on broader issues, including Georgia's future EU accession.

The main shortcomings relate to gaps in the assistance schemes and errors in program design. There is a lack of psychological support, and some returnees do not receive adequate information during the pre-return phase. Additionally, the feasibility of income-generating projects is not always properly assessed. In certain cases, business plans are evaluated abroad without a full understanding of local market conditions or cultural realities in Georgia. Furthermore, returnees may face social stigma, as there are either negative attitudes within Georgian society towards those who did not stay abroad and were forced to return or high expectations about the affluency of emigrants.

KEY LESSONS

Synergy of actors is key to effective reintegration. The most effective reintegration solutions depend on a synergy of resources provided by various actors working at different levels, with a clear and suitable division of responsibilities. In the case of Georgia, this is illustrated by the complementary roles of Frontex, state institutions, and locally based NGOs.

Pre-return preparation determines post-return success. Reintegration begins at the pre-return stage, where effective communication between return-enforcement authorities and implementing partners is essential for adequately preparing to receive returnees. In Georgia's case, coordinated information exchange between Frontex and local stakeholders enables reintegration measures to be designed according to actual needs and local conditions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Provide relevant and timely access to information. Strengthening access to relevant information before departure seems crucial for an effective reintegration process. This information should be accessible in strategic places of first contact, like airports, railway stations, and bus stations.

Offer pre-departure training to facilitate employment. Training should be available before departure, so the returnees are prepared to find a job immediately after arrival.

Conduct information campaigns to improve social acceptance. Organising targeted information campaigns can help alter public perceptions and foster a more supportive environment for returnees.

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Name of practice	Reintegration programs	
Dates	2023 - present	
Target group	Returnees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Iraq
	Regions	Asia
	Sub Region	Middle East
Actor	Migration and Displacement Ministry	
Return Stages	Post-Return	
Challenge addressed	Reintegration Sustainability Governance, Cooperation, and Coordination	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Migrants' Agency Human-rights-based approach	

SUMMARY

The National Referral Mechanism is a comprehensive initiative designed to assist returning individuals upon their arrival in Iraq. It facilitates access to their rights and the benefits provided by the Iraqi government, which include healthcare, education, legal support, vocational training services, psychological assistance, employment opportunities, and all necessary elements for successful reintegration. The Mechanism is fully supported and operated by the government and is supervised by the Ministry of Migration and Displacement, with the collaboration of various other ministries, such as Planning, Labour and Social Affairs, Health, Education, Interior, and Higher Education, as well as Iraqi security institutions. Although it is a relatively new mechanism, it plays a crucial role for returnees and offers key features such as connecting them with relevant ministries and non-governmental organizations and providing free services to all returnees from abroad.

These services include individual counselling, referrals to service providers, follow-up assistance during the reintegration process, help in establishing small businesses, employment, vocational and educational training, housing support, legal assistance, protection, medical and mental health support, and help with enrolling children in school. Overall, the Mechanism aims to preserve the dignity and rights of returnees.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

Since 2023, the National Referral Mechanism has achieved several benefits. It has strengthened coordination across government ministries, institutions, and international and local organisations, replacing previously fragmented responses with a more coherent support framework for returnees.

The NRM has facilitated access to health, education, and social services through targeted referrals: of the 2,000 individuals registered, 1,300 received direct support, including document restoration and correction of identification papers; 700 obtained cash assistance; 20 were referred for residency cards and 40 for national identity cards; 20 accessed healthcare; 20 received school-related documentation and re-entry support; and 500 were referred for training and, in some cases, small business loans.

Through this structure, the NRM has contributed to safeguarding fundamental rights for all individuals irrespective of status, reinforcing alignment with international human rights standards. It has also introduced a monitoring and evaluation system that tracks each case and reassesses progress every six months, improving oversight and service effectiveness. Finally, the NRM has created a central database of returnees, enhancing the availability of accurate, up-to-date information on their profiles and needs.

The NRM has also revealed several structural shortcomings. Coordination and communication gaps persist, with returnees frequently arriving at Baghdad International Airport without advance notice to Iraqi authorities, creating confusion and hindering the reception committee's work. Limited government funding constrains the NRM's ability to deliver services effectively, while the insufficient involvement of civil society organisations weakens complementary psychosocial, social, and training support. The mechanism's focus on Baghdad alone, coupled with a shortage of reception and support centres in the governorates, complicates transport and follow-up for returnees across the country, including those returning to the Kurdistan Region of Iraq.

Awareness of the NRM remains low, reducing uptake of available services among returnees. Broader weaknesses in Iraq's public infrastructure, particularly in health, education, housing, and employment, further restrict the NRM's capacity to provide a suitable environment for returnees. Excessive bureaucracy and administrative routines contribute to frustration and diminish confidence in the mechanism, while limited information-sharing and low mutual trust between host countries and Iraq, especially concerning security, identity, and health data, continue to impede effective coordination.

The NRM has significantly improved the protection of returnees' human and legal rights by establishing a formal framework. However, gaps in coordination and communication can weaken these protections. While it has aided economic and social stabilization for many returnees, funding constraints limit the scale and consistency of these efforts.

The NRM has strengthened cooperation between Iraq and international organisations like the IOM and UNHCR, enhancing returnees' trust in state institutions. Nonetheless, low awareness of the mechanism and uneven service delivery threaten this confidence. It has also improved data collection on returnees, although incomplete coordination with governorates and the Kurdistan Region may hinder data flow. Overall, the NRM showcases Iraq's commitment to international obligations, positively affecting the country's global standing.

KEY LESSONS

Effective return systems depend on strong communication and prior coordination between host and receiving states. When advance information-sharing is weak or inconsistent, reception procedures are disrupted, service delivery is delayed, and authorities face avoidable operational difficulties.

Decentralised reception capacity is essential for effective service delivery and follow-up. While centralisation supports quality control and data management, any country implementing return programmes should ensure the presence of local reception and support centres to facilitate timely assistance and continuous monitoring. In the case of Iraq, while centralisation supports quality assurance and data control, establishing reception and support centres in the governorates and the Kurdistan Region has been essential for timely assistance and effective monitoring.

Transparent information and proactive outreach are critical to ensure returnees have access to available services. Awareness gaps significantly reduce programme uptake; therefore, media outreach must be systematically integrated into all assistance and referral mechanisms.

Reintegration mechanisms cannot succeed without an enabling economic and social environment and meaningful civil society engagement. Even robust referral systems may be undermined by systemic unemployment, poverty, weak public services, or limited NGO involvement in their provision. Continuous monitoring and evaluation are therefore essential to identify gaps, adjust interventions, and make sure that returnees, particularly the most vulnerable, receive the necessary assistance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthen international coordination and information exchange. Effective return mechanisms require clear, transparent protocols with host countries and robust information-sharing systems to ensure smooth, rights-respecting returns. In Iraq, this includes formal agreements with host states, secure data management, and enhanced cooperation on security, identity, and health information.

Expand and decentralise reception and support infrastructure. Returnees benefit from accessible reception, psychosocial, and reintegration services beyond central locations. In Iraq, establishing centres in major governorates and the Kurdistan Region of Iraq will facilitate timely assistance, continuous monitoring, and better integration outcomes.

Secure sufficient resources and enable civil society participation. Adequate funding, staff capacity, and engagement of NGOs are critical to provide comprehensive services, including psychosocial support, legal assistance, and awareness-raising for returnees. For Iraq, this entails increasing government budget allocations, seeking international support, and integrating civil society in complementary service delivery.

Promote awareness, simplify procedures, and strengthen monitoring. Transparent communication, streamlined administrative procedures, and continuous monitoring improve trust, reduce inefficiencies, and support effective reintegration. In Iraq, this includes raising awareness of the NRM, reducing bureaucratic barriers in document issuance, and establishing independent monitoring and evaluation mechanisms

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Name of practice	Post-return policies	
Dates	(No Information)	
Target group	Returnees	
Geographic Scope	Country	Nigeria
	Regions	Africa
	Sub Region	West Africa
Actor	Patriotic Citizen Initiative	
Return Stages	Post-Return	
Challenge addressed	Governance, Cooperation and Coordination Reintegration Sustainability	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Vulnerability & child-centred approach Human-rights-based approach	

SUMMARY

Patriotic Citizen Initiatives collaborates with the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), IOM, and other CSOs through Nigeria's National Referral Mechanism to provide psychosocial counselling, vocational training, and long-term monitoring of returnees in Lagos (South West) and Benin City (South South).

Working with the International Labour Organization (ILO), PCI provides training and capacity-building for returnees, particularly those assisted by IOM. These programmes equip migrants with market-relevant skills and viable business ideas, helping them adapt to Nigeria's challenging economic conditions and avoid re-trafficking or renewed irregular migration.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

PCI strengthens Nigeria's migration governance by integrating psychosocial support, protection, and economic empowerment for returnees. Through collaboration with NCFRMI, IOM, NAPTIP, and civil society networks, PCI provides counselling, vocational training, and family reintegration, while specialised profiling ensures trafficked persons receive tailored support. Partnerships with the ILO equip returnees with practical skills and viable business ideas that foster economic independence. These efforts improve mental health, reduce stigma, lower risks of re-trafficking and irregular migration, and anchor reintegration in local communities. At the institutional level, PCI's work reinforces national coordination mechanisms and makes reintegration processes more humane, sustainable, and resilient.

KEY LESSONS

Multistakeholder support is fundamental for successful returnee integration. While challenges of sustainability and scale remain, the practice identified above shows that attention to migrants' vulnerabilities before return, coupled with holistic, community-anchored reintegration afterwards, can significantly reduce risks of re-trafficking, stigma, and irregular re-migration. The practice also underscores the importance of linking return and reintegration to broader employment creation and development policies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Adopt holistic and sustainable reintegration approaches. Reintegration is most effective when it combines psychosocial support, protection for trafficked persons, and economic empowerment. In Nigeria, civil society organisations like PCI should be supported for their grassroots role, while the National Referral Mechanism must be strengthened to ensure consistent services across regions.

Expand skills development and community engagement. Vocational training and entrepreneurship programs are essential to reduce re-trafficking and irregular migration. Reintegration strategies should actively involve families and communities to counter stigma, and long-term monitoring systems should track outcomes to measure effectiveness.

Strengthen coordination and regional cooperation. Effective reintegration benefits from robust cross-border collaboration. In Nigeria, stronger regional engagement within ECOWAS and with international partners would improve protection, referrals, and coordination for returnees.

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Name of practice	Reintegration programs		
Dates	2023 - present		
Target group	Returnees		
Geographic Scope	Country	Afghanistan	
	Regions	Asia	
	Sub Region	South Asia	
Actor	Ministry of Refugee and Reintegration High Commission on Returnees		
Return Stages	Post-Return		
Challenge addressed	Governance, Coordination and	Cooperation,	
	Reintegration Sustainability Institutional Capacity and Resources		
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Accountability Human-rights-based approach		

SUMMARY

As of 2025, the current political authority has framed return as a national priority, establishing a High Commission on Returnees within the Ministry of Refugees and Returnees (MoRR), which operates under cabinet-level oversight.

Operations are concentrated at key border points, such as Torkham, Jalalabad province bordering Pakistan, Spin Boldak, Kandahar province bordering Pakistan, Islam Qala, Herat province bordering Iran, linked to reception camps like Anzargi and Omari temporary settlement camps. The High Commission follows a structured workflow: people are first registered and screened at the “zero point,” then provided with immediate relief and basic protection, transported onward to camps or destination provinces, given temporary shelter and essential services, assessed and placed in education, supported with targeted cash assistance, and, where applicable, allocated land on a per-household member basis .

At each stage, international and non-state national aid organisations, particularly the UN agencies, play a critical role. For example, UNHCR leads on registration, emergency shelter, and cash or in-kind assistance; IOM focuses on safe transit, immediate relief, and support to vulnerable groups; and organisations such as the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC), along with other UN agencies, INGOs and local NGOs, provide counselling, legal aid, and socio-economic support. Together, these actors deliver life-saving emergency assistance both at the border “zero points” and in destination provinces, helping returnees meet their basic needs and begin the process of reintegration.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

Although the High Commission and the Ministry of Refugees and Repatriation (MoRR) have established legal and policy frameworks for return and reintegration, significant implementation gaps persist. Many rights and protection standards remain unrealised, and the dissolution of MoRR’s Directorate of Gender Affairs has further reduced the government’s ability to address gender-specific risks and vulnerabilities.

MoRR and the High Commission face major capacity constraints, and the effectiveness of new structures, particularly the High Commission and its twelve IEA-era sub-committees, remains uncertain and under-documented. This lack of clarity undermines coherent, nationwide coordination among state bodies responsible for return and reintegration.

Most assistance delivered under High Commission coordination remains short-term emergency support rather than sustainable, long-term economic or social programmes. Consequently, many returnees remain unemployed, financially precarious, and dependent on informal coping mechanisms instead of durable, state-led solutions.

Humanitarian access challenges further constrain the response. Non-state organisations and UN agencies face significant obstacles in delivering emergency assistance due to weak coordination with state institutions and restrictive policies, especially those limiting women's right to work. These restrictions prevent female humanitarian staff from reaching women and children, disrupting life-saving programmes at border points and in destination communities, and leave the most vulnerable returnees with only partial or no access to essential services.

Finally, the provision of adequate resources, training, and technical support to address and oversee the return and reintegration processes appears difficult due to the legal and policy deadlock created by the non-recognition of the Taliban government by the international community, including the United Nations.

KEY LESSONS

Coordination, Collaboration, and Burden-Sharing. The Afghan experience shows that large-scale and unpredictable return flows, coupled with limited institutional and financial capacity, cannot be managed by the government alone. The lack of effective joint planning and coordination between Afghan authorities and international agencies highlights the need for genuine hybrid approaches in which responsibility for protection and reintegration is shared.

Returnee-Inclusive Interventions. Returnees in Afghanistan have largely remained excluded from policy processes and decision-making bodies. This underscores the importance of developing returnee-led frameworks that ensure reintegration policies are tailored to their needs, experiences, and priorities, and that returnees have a meaningful voice in shaping the support they receive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthen institutional and operational capacity. Authorities responsible for return and reintegration should reinforce their institutional, managerial and financial capacity at both national and sub-national levels to effectively coordinate large-scale return flows. This includes establishing clear roles and responsibilities, improving inter-agency coordination with UN bodies and NGOs, and guaranteeing humanitarian access in line with humanitarian principles. In Afghanistan, this requires targeted support to MoRR, the High Commission and provincial structures, including joint coordination platforms and guaranteed access for humanitarian actors, including women aid workers.

Invest in sustainable, returnee-inclusive reintegration packages. Move beyond short-term emergency assistance by scaling up tailored reintegration support that combines vocational training, business start-up assistance, and employment creation, particularly for youth and women. These programmes should guarantee access to basic services, including healthcare, education, and adequate housing, and be designed in consultation with returnees and host communities, not just for them.

Establish evidence-based, coordinated regional policy frameworks. States experiencing large-scale return flows should develop regional mechanisms to collect reliable data, support policy dialogue, and guide sustainable, rights-based reintegration frameworks and programmes. Engagement of governments, international agencies, and civil society is required to promote policies that are coordinated, evidence-informed, and responsive to the needs of both returnees and host communities. In Afghanistan, the establishment of a Return and Reintegration Research and Policy Centre could bring together state and non-state institutions, UN agencies, the EU, and key host countries (such as Türkiye, Pakistan and Iran) with the aim of generating data, facilitating dialogue, and designing adequate frameworks.

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Name of practice	National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum	
Dates	2014-2023/2024	
Target group	Moroccan returnees, foreign migrants regularised	
Geographic Scope	Country	Morocco
	Regions	Africa
	Sub Region	North Africa
Actor	National Government, Local-Authorities International and local NGOs	
Return Stages	Post-Return	
Challenge addressed	Reintegration Sustainability	
Principles referred (implicit or explicit)	Migrants' Agency Human-rights-based approach	

SUMMARY

The 2014 National Immigration and Asylum Strategy (NIAS – SNIA, in French) represents the first comprehensive, rights-based migration framework in the MENA–African region. It combined asylum reform, large-scale regularisation campaigns, and structured access to public services, including health, education, employment, and vocational training. The strategy aimed to manage irregular migration flows, regularise migrants' status, reduce the number of people living without legal residency, curb human trafficking and smuggling networks, and reposition Morocco's image in Africa.

The NIAS was operationalised through a set of thematic programmes, often cited as 11 priority domains, covering health, education, housing, legal protection, labour, governance, and cooperation. Implementation has been staged via national action plans and ad hoc measures. Key steps included two major regularisation campaigns (2014 and 2017) and subsequent action plans (e.g., 2018–2020 and 2021–2023), translating SNIA goals into concrete measures.

While the NIAS can be considered a “good practice,” this assessment is conditional and dependent on the context of Moroccan-European relations at the time, and the strategy is better understood as a promising, norm-setting policy experiment rather than a fully realised model of migrant integration.

BENEFITS/IMPACTS AND SHORTCOMINGS

Following the adoption of NIAS, Moroccan authorities facilitated returnees' and migrants' access to healthcare, basic education, and certain social services, at least for those who had obtained regular status. Efforts were also made to issue residency documents and refugee or temporary protection cards to asylum seekers. The strategy created an institutional framework that enabled greater involvement of NGOs, municipalities, and international partners—including IOM, UNHCR, and the EU—in implementation, assistance programs, and capacity-building initiatives. The NIAS promoted a blend of human rights and humanitarian protection, integration, development, and improved governance, while also reflecting Morocco's European migration policy and African diplomacy, helping reposition the country as a leader in welcoming and respecting migrants' rights.

Implementation remained partial and uneven, both geographically and over time. Many migrants—particularly those who remained irregular—continued to face legal, economic, and social vulnerabilities. Some observers have noted that Morocco’s approach relied on periodic “exceptional” regularisation campaigns rather than steady, institutionalised pathways, raising questions about long-term sustainability. Persistent gaps also remained in labour-market integration, delays in establishing a fully operational national asylum system, and tensions between protection objectives and intensified EU-Morocco border-control cooperation.

KEY LESSONS

Migration policies should prioritise human dignity alongside security. Effective migration management requires balancing protection, inclusion, and rights with enforcement objectives. In Morocco, the NSIA set a precedent by openly framing migration governance around dignity, human rights, and social inclusion rather than solely focusing on border control and security.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Sustainable migration policies require shared ownership and multi-level cooperation. To strengthen long-term viability, migration strategies should actively involve local authorities and elected officials, be supported by stronger regional cooperation across neighbouring and origin countries and be accompanied by sustained engagement from international partners. In the Moroccan context, this translates into deeper local political ownership, enhanced Maghreb and African cooperation, and more consistent European involvement.

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